

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report

M4.1 A detailed outline of the guides that will be developed during this period

Document info

Title	A detailed outline of the guides that will be developed during this period
Deliverable/Milestone Number	M4.1
Responsible Participant	Patricia Palagi
WP Number	WP4
Dissemination level (PU/RE/CO / or NA)	P

*For types of deliverables please see [Guidelines for ELIXIR Commissioned Services](#)

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1		21.11.2024	Draft started by Patricia Palagi
1.0	NA	08.01.2025	Final Patricia Palagi
	Content Check by WP1	24.01.2025	ok'ed during ExCo call

Author List

Node (ISO 2 letter country code or (eg: EMBL-EBI)	Institute (no address)	Name, surname	ORCID	Email
CH	SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	Palagi, Patricia	0000-0001-9062-6303	Patricia.Palagi@sib.swiss

Abbreviations and Acronyms

TtT	ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer
-----	---------------------------------

Contents

Document info	1
Version history	1
Author List	1
Executive Summary	2
Practical guides for Train the Trainer courses	2
Dissemination Plans	3

Executive Summary

This milestone provides a detailed outline of the TtT guides that will be developed during the period from Jan 2025 to July 2026.

Practical guides for Train the Trainer courses

The ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer (TtT) [program](#) fosters a network of trainers, the TtT community, to allow them to benefit from reciprocal support and exchange of experiences. The TtT instructors teach the regular and standard TtT courses, which aim to give new trainers/teachers tools and tips for providing an enriching learning experience to trainees, irrespective of topic, and to include best-practice guidance on course and training material development.

The TtT courses are composed of four core sessions:

1. Principles of learning and how they apply to training;
2. Design of engaging sessions, materials and courses;
3. Training techniques for enhancing learner engagement and participation;
4. Assessment and feedback in training.

Today, the TtT instructors teach the TtT courses using the training materials in the form of a set of Google slides, shared docs, and survey forms available in a [Reference folder](#). New TtT instructors joining the TtT community learn how to teach these sessions by studying this set of slides, observing how other instructors train, and discussing the content in TtT instructors' community

meetings. More experienced instructors can also mentor them before they feel they are ready to deliver the TtT course sessions (usually one session after the other, and with those they feel more comfortable with).

We aim to create accompanying “Teaching instructions” guides detailing each TtT session and explaining how to teach each. For instance, these guides will contain explanations on how to run the exercises, the minimum requirements for each lesson, and the rationale for the topics being taught, among others.

By the end of July 2026, we will have four guides, one for each of the above TtT sessions, available on ELIXIR Training Platform GitHub and following the ELIXIR Lesson Template format. We will benefit from the TtT Mentoring program, which will start in January 2025, and the mentoring work that will be done by the mentors and mentees, to create the guides. Their learning process, questions, and usage of the materials will be used to make the guide contents.

We will release the guides according to the following plan:

Title of the “Teaching instructions” guide / TtT session	Deadline of release
Principles of learning and how they apply to training	Oct 2025
Design of engaging sessions, materials and courses	Dec 2025
Training techniques for enhancing learner engagement and participation	Mar 2026
Assessment and feedback in training	June 2026

Dissemination Plans

We will ensure these guides are in F1000R and they are disseminated throughout the TtT instructor’s community and the ELIXIR Training Platform members via email, the Slack channels. We will also disseminate these guides when we teach a TtT course.